

Appendix A.2: Amended inclusion and exclusion criteria – update 07.10.24

**Revised after interrater comparison of country results*

	Training programmes	Training materials
Inclusion	<p>Geographical: provided by a university within an ERA country</p> <p>Quality: - Provided by a university ranked by THE 15 and QS 16 in 2024 - Up to date and in line with current scientific and technical understanding</p> <p>Time frame: course provided in academic year 2023/2024</p> <p>Language: must be identifiable using English language search queries. Once identified, non-English content will be translated into English</p> <p>Content: - Must discuss key climate and environmental concerns applicable to either the processes or outputs of R&I, and/or as an RE&RI consideration - Discussion should, at minimum, consist of engagement with these topics either as themes running throughout a programme, or as one defined section of focus within a broader programme</p>	<p>Geographical: accessible to ERA-based users</p> <p>Quality: Up to date and in line with current scientific and technical understanding</p> <p>Time frame: published during or since 2015</p> <p>Language: must be identifiable using English language search queries. Once identified, non-English content will be translated into English</p> <p>Content: - Must discuss key climate and environmental concerns applicable to either the processes or outputs of R&I, and/or as an RE&RI consideration - Discussion should, at minimum, consist of engagement with these topics either as themes running throughout training materials, or as one defined section of focus within broader training materials</p> <p>Access: publicly and freely available (including on websites where a free account is required for access)</p> <p>Content type: text, video, audio (including descriptions of other formats, e.g. exhibitions, workshops, etc.)</p>

Training courses and materials for a research ethics and integrity informed green transition in Europe: a scoping review and gap analysis

		<p>Target audience: university students, researchers/scientists, citizen scientists, teachers/trainers, ethics reviewers</p>
<p>Exclusion</p>	<p>Geographical: provided by a university outside the ERA</p> <p>Quality: - Provided by a university other than those ranked by THE 15 and QS 16 in 2024 - Out of date due to technological advances or developments in scientific understanding</p> <p>Time frame: course provided in the academic year 2022/2023 or earlier</p> <p>Language: no identifying information available in English</p> <p>Content: - No relevance for R&I - Discussion of R&I but no relevance for RE&RI or substantial engagement with climate and environmental concerns - Relevant topics discussed from an overwhelmingly management, business, financial, tourism or development perspective</p>	<p>Geographical: not accessible to ERA-based users</p> <p>Quality: Out of date due to technological developments or developments in scientific understanding</p> <p>Time frame: Published during or before 2014</p> <p>Language: no identifying information available in English</p> <p>Content: - No relevance for R&I - Discussion of R&I but no relevance for RE&RI or substantial engagement with climate and environmental - Relevant topics discussed from an overwhelmingly management, business, financial, tourism or development perspective</p> <p>Access: paywalled content</p> <p>Content type: books, articles (unless used as case studies), theses, blog posts, news items, guidelines, statements or policies</p> <p>Target audience: all categories other than those mentioned in the inclusion criteria</p>